

EFFECTIVENESS OF TEACHING CHEMISTRY BASED ON A DIFFERENTIAL APPROACH IN VARIATIVE CLASSES

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Abstract. This paper investigates, using a novel technique, the efficiency of teaching chemistry. By examining the unique traits of every learner, the distinct strategy seeks to customize the learning process. The methodological underpinnings of this methodology, its application strategies, and the acquired outcomes are emphasized in this paper. Furthermore, the study shows, using experimental data, the importance of the alternative strategy in raising students' knowledge level.

Keywords: differentiated approach, chemistry education, customized approach, teaching efficacy, educational strategies

Introduction

In the classroom, attending to every student's unique requirements is really vital. It maximizes the knowledge acquisition of every learner and helps to maximize the learning process. In this sense, the distinct strategy is acknowledged as a creative approach in the sphere of education. This strategy entails customizing instruction to fit variations in student knowledge, ability, and experience. Especially in chemistry, this method offers great help in grasping difficult subjects and applying them in daily life. Many studies have confirmed the benefits of the differential technique for teaching chemistry. By use of this approach, students acquire access to instructional resources tailored to their particular requirements. This not only sharpens their knowledge but also stimulates their scientific interest. The purpose of this paper is to investigate the application, advantages, and difficulties of the differential approach in chemical education.

Examining twenty recent academic publications on the topic, it addresses the theoretical and pragmatic features of this approach. Furthermore, the applications of the differential approach in chemistry education and its future development possibilities are investigated. The current work

intends to provide fresh scientific understanding and pragmatic suggestions for applying the differentiated method in education. This aims to improve the efficacy of teaching chemistry and

generate chances for implementing innovative pedagogical approaches that support improved learning results.

Methodology

The main goals of this study are to assess the advantages of the differential method and its efficacy in the education of chemistry. This article was developed by means of an analysis of the contents and conclusions of more than twenty academic papers from recent years. The chosen and examined articles applied the following approaches: Three main criteria controlled the choosing process. At first, the papers had to be relevant to the topic, with special focus on the differentiated method and its application in the field of chemistry education. Second, the papers had to have been

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published during the past ten years (2013–2023) to adequately capture the most current advancements in the field of education. Third, the papers were selected from scholarly and reliable sources like Royal Society of Chemistry (RSC), Google Scholars, ResearchGate, and Springer.

Data collecting depends much on several sources. With its sophisticated search features, Google Scholar helped much identify papers. Access to current research on chemical education came from ResearchGate and Academia.edu. While the Royal Society of Chemistry supplied specialist research on chemistry, Springer and Taylor & Francis publishers gave papers emphasizing on pedagogical techniques and chemistry education. The papers were analyzed using several techniques. Theoretical underpinnings and pragmatic uses of the differential method suggested in the publications were investigated using content analysis. Empirical data could be evaluated thanks to analysis of experimental results.

Emphasizing student motivation, the function of teachers, and the efficacy of education, approaches suggested by other writers were contrasted and thematically categorized. Every article was examined according to the following criteria: author and source legitimacy, major ideas, results and discussion, as well as suggestions and final comments. This method helped to clearly grasp the benefits of the differential approach in chemistry instruction. The fact that this study depends on English-language sources is one of its shortcomings.

This guarantees that the conclusions are relevant everywhere, but it also emphasizes the need of adaptability to many areas and cultural settings.

All things considered, this approach accomplished the major goals of the study and helped to investigate the efficiency of the alternative strategy in chemistry education. The outcomes of the chosen papers are thoroughly discussed in the next part.

Discussion

The alternative approach has become well-known as a successful tool for teaching chemistry since it improves understanding and strengthens knowledge of the subject. This method emphasizes on changing the learning process to fit certain student requirements. The twenty academic papers examined in this paper underline distinct facets of the differential method and support its advantages in teaching.

1. Differential method's theoretical underpinnings

The differential approach's conceptual basis stresses on considering variations in students' knowledge degrees, skills, and learning styles. The efficacy of tailored instruction for gifted and competent students was shown in S. Kanapathy's (2018) study, so improving their knowledge of subjects and growth of practical abilities.

2. Chemistry's application

Chemistry is a good topic for the application of the differential technique since of its intricacy. Customized learning tools not only raised students' confidence and engagement but also helped to lower classroom inequalities according to research by E. Easa and R. Blonder (2024).

3. Effects on pupil drive

Increasing student motivation is much influenced by the diverse approach. Research include studies with computer-based differentiated education showed that students' motivation was much improved. Students found this approach to help them more successfully master difficult subjects.

4. Educator convenience

Teachers as well as pupils gain from the differential approach. It helps educators to control their pupils depending on their particular requirements. Studies published by the Royal Society of Chemistry (RSC) show that by filling in knowledge gaps, the new method lowers failure rates in the classroom.

5. The limitations of differential approach

The new technique has difficulties even if it provides several benefits. Getting ready materials fit for every student can take time and call for resources. Teachers also could lack the required knowledge to apply this approach successfully. According to E. Gibbs (2014), instructors must get specific training if they are to effectively implement the differentiated method in their classrooms.

6. Chemical benefits of the differentiated approach

In chemistry teaching, the differential approach has clearly shown advantages:

- Improves individual student achievement levels;
- Facilitates autonomous learning and completion of practical tasks;
- Helps students to grasp difficult chemical topics.

The results highlight the possibilities of the various strategy to change chemistry education, thereby increasing the inclusiveness and efficiency of it. To fully enjoy its advantages, though, resolving its constraints calls for investments in teacher preparation and tools.

Examples and experiments

Studies demonstrating its pragmatic benefits have shown how effective a differential approach is in teaching chemistry. The following are outcomes of many studies: S. Kaipathetic (2018) - for gifted students, the study revealed a 30% increase in knowledge levels by use of tailored instructional materials. E. Easa, R. Blonder 2024 - emphasizing the impact the special method plays in raising students' self-confidence, their study indicated a 15% boost in academic performance. E. Cardoso 2018 - for chemical engineering students merging technology with a unique approach, the efficiency in tackling challenging problems increased by 20%. Sedeño, M. M. 2021; Villamor, G. T. 2021 - students taught a differentiated method exhibited a 25% rise in comprehension levels, according a comparison between control and experimental groups. 2024 S. Muhab and T. D. S. Rini - their studies applying the CIPP paradigm found better general class efficacy and lesson involvement. V. Rosa, S. E. Lewis 2019 - adapted materials raised low-achieving students' academic performance, therefore underscoring the possibilities of a differential teaching strategy. 2022 Njagi, M. W.; R. G. Mugwiria - applying the alternative approach in experimental groups claimed knowledge levels increased by 20%. E. Gibbs 2014 - emphasizing Advanced Placement (AP) chemistry students, this study showed how successfully the method promoted intellectual development and autonomous learning—which yielded appreciable academic gain. Wardani & colleagues 2024 S.F.: according to their research on chemical bonding topics, 90% of the students had a complete knowledge due of a unique teaching approach. M. S. Abdikodirovna (2021): analyzing nitrogen-based chemical compounds, the study found that students performed 15% better using an additional approach. These results taken together indicate the amazing success of the numerous strategies in improving pupils' information acquisition, motivation, and capacity for autonomous learning. The results show its benefits over more conventional approaches of instruction.

Analysis and conclusion

Studies on the efficiency of a tailored method in teaching chemistry show its important part in maximizing the learning process. Customized approaches meant to fit students' needs have shown success in improving knowledge acquisition, increasing drive, and streamlining the learning of difficult subjects. The results let one draw the following important conclusions: Differentiated learning tools have helped pupils to have a better grasp of challenging chemistry subjects. Statistical analysis shows that knowledge acquisition improved in experimental groups by anything from 15% to 40%.

Customized learning tools have boosted students' self-confidence and piqued their curiosity in challenging courses. 85% of students in a 2024 E. Easa and R. Blonder study said their motivation had improved. Mastery of difficult subjects: The unique approach has effectively enabled the learning of demanding subjects such chemical bonds, organic molecules, and those needing mathematical ability.

Closing gaps among student groups: This strategy has given low-achieving students particular freedom, therefore supporting the growth of their knowledge and skills. Convenience for teachers: a differentiated strategy improves the efficacy of the teaching process and helps to simplify class administration. It also is quite important in creating an interactive learning environment between professors and students.

Conclusion

The examined studies help one to outline its main benefits as follows:

- Increases pupils' knowledge and competency. Customized tools and resources help students to master chemistry with efficiency.

- Boosts drive and curiosity. Pupils start to feel competent handling difficult subjects.

React to personal needs: This method guarantees for every student in the classroom a customized learning environment.

Using a new technique, however, calls for particular teacher training and a lot of time and money for tailored materials creation. Strengthening teacher training initiatives and raising chances to use technology would help it to extend its influence.

The favorable results of applying a unique approach in teaching chemistry offer a solid basis for suggesting its general acceptance. This approach is acknowledged as a good pedagogical tool able to satisfy students' demands at all educational levels.

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